

MATERIAL USED: UNDERSTANDABILITY ASSESSMENT

Consideration: The questionnaires were implemented in the MUSS web-platform¹.

M1. Suggestion, Claims, Petitions or Complaints System

1. **Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.**

- "Sent response" is the last event before finishing the process, regardless of the previous process flow.
- The "Process request" event occurs immediately after the request is classified as "Proceed Immediately".
- If a request has been classified, then it can be classified again.
- If a request is classified as "Suggestion", then at any time, it will execute the "Contact requester" event.

¹ http://muss.informatica.uv.cl/execution_experiment

M2. Applicants for a position System

- Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.
 - In order to schedule medical examination, it is necessary to reject the references.
 - The area manager supports the interview scheduling event.
 - The applicant only can accept salary offer.
 - If the process of checking results it is necessary to add more information, another interview can be scheduled.

M3. Travel Request System

1. Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.

- A request that has been rejected can be re-evaluated.
- If the request was rejected the process ends
- The "Notify employees" event can be executed only if the request was rejected.
- The SV05 event represents an exclusive choice event, that is, it does not allow both internal processes to run.

M4. Purchase Request System

1. Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.

- The process ends when "rejected request" event is executed.
- To "Approve request" there must be a "Reject" previously.
- The "Add reason for rejected" and "Send notification" events are executed in different flows.

The flow represented by event SCE03 indicates that both internal events must be executed to continue the process.

M5. Vacation Request System

1. Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.

- If a rejection notification is sent, the "Update payroll system" event cannot be executed.
- If the event "Send vacation request voucher" is executed, the request cannot be rejected
- The event "Update payroll system " is the only flow that permits the end of the process.
- If "Send vacation request voucher" is executed, the "Verify days available" event must have been executed immediately before.

M6. Payment System

1. Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.

- There is a flow within the process that allows to resubmit a revision of a purchase order.
- If any product and/or service requires approval, then the "Update ERP Financial" event will not be executed.
- The actor "Treasury" supports the event "Approval products and/or services."
- The PF06 event indicates that each of its internal events is mutually exclusive.

M7. Photo Agency System

- Based on the model, answer the following questions. You have seven minutes.
 - The "Board management" actor is who initiates the interaction in the "Resolve applications" event.
 - To execute "return signed exclusive note" event, there must be approved applications.
 - If a request is rejected, there are another flow allows to continue with the process.
 - If a request is rejected, the "Request assignment of exclusive" event will be executed.